

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 13.03.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.05.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (119), 1031-1051

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.15567467

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ROR Id: <https://ror.org/01a0mk874>

Soil Temperature Distribution at Different Depths in the Thracian Peninsula and Trend Analysis (1990-2023)

Trakya Yarımadası'nda Farklı Derinliklere Göre Toprak Sıcaklıklarının Dağılışı ve Trend Analizi (1990-2023)

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the monthly and annual variation of long-term average soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths in the Thracian Peninsula and tested trend analyses. To this end, 34 years (1990-2023) of data from 13 meteorological stations were utilized. Mann-Kendall Test, Kendall's Tau, and Sen's Slope tests were used for trend analysis of soil temperatures. Therefore, it was aimed to reveal the effects of global climate change and global warming on soil temperatures at different depths in the Thracian Peninsula. The study revealed that soil temperature changes were similar to the changes in air temperature; soil temperatures were consistently above the annual average air temperature values, and the difference between soil temperature and air temperature varied between 1.1 °C and 3.4 °C. Annual average soil temperatures in the Thracian Peninsula exhibit a "thermal temperature regime" characteristic. In the Thracian Peninsula, monthly average soil temperatures vary with depth, but generally show a significant and positive trend in the 7-month period between September and March. The trend analysis results indicate a statistically significant and positive trend in the annual average soil temperatures of all stations except Kumköy and Sarıyer. These test results are consistent with the significant and positive trend detected in the trend analysis of annual average air temperatures in the Thracian Peninsula. Planning for the impacts of the increasing trend in soil temperatures on agricultural activities and natural systems in the Thracian Peninsula should be done without delay. They can also use soil temperature trends to promote the mitigation of various predicted environmental problems, such as seasonal temperature fluctuations, water scarcity, irrigation demands, and crop rotation.

Keywords: Thracian Peninsula, Soil, Temperature, Trend, Analysis.

ÖZET

Bu çalışmada, Trakya Yarımadası'nın 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm ve 100 cm derinliklerde uzun yıllık ortalama toprak sıcaklıklarının aylık ve yıllık değişimi araştırılmış ve trend analizleri test edilmiştir. Bu amaçla, 13 meteoroloji istasyonuna ait 34 yıllık (1990-2023) verilerden yararlanılmıştır. Toprak sıcaklıklarının trend analizinde yöntem olarak Mann-Kendall Testi, Kendall'ın Tau ve Sen'in Eğim testleri kullanılmıştır. Böylece küresel iklim değişikliği ve küresel ısınmanın Trakya Yarımadası'nda farklı derinliklerdeki toprak sıcaklıkları üzerinde etkilerinin ortaya çıkarılması amaçlanmıştır. Araştırmada toprak sıcaklığı değişimlerinin hava sıcaklığındaki değişime benzerlik gösterdiği, toprak sıcaklıklarının yıllık ortalama hava sıcaklığı değerlerinin devamlı üstünde olduğu ve toprak sıcaklığı ile hava sıcaklığı arasındaki farkın 1.1 °C ile 3.4 °C arasında değiştiği tespit edilmiştir. Yıllık ortalama toprak sıcaklıkları bakımından Trakya Yarımadası'nın topraklarında "Termik Sıcaklık Rejimi" görülmektedir. Trakya Yarımadası'nda aylık ortalama toprak sıcaklıkları derinliğe göre değişmekle birlikte genelde eylül-mart arasındaki 7 aylık dönemde anlamlı ve pozitif yönlü bir eğilim göstermektedir. Trend analiz sonuçlarına göre Kumköy ve Sarıyer haricindeki bütün istasyonların yıllık ortalama toprak sıcaklıklarında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve pozitif yönlü bir trend görülmektedir. Bu test sonucu Trakya Yarımadası'ndaki yıllık ortalama hava sıcaklıklarının trend analizlerinde de tespit edilen anlamlı ve pozitif yönlü trend ile uyumludur. Toprak sıcaklıklarındaki artış eğiliminin Trakya Yarımadası'ndaki tarımsal faaliyetler ve doğal sistemler üzerindeki etkileriyle ilgili planlamaların hiç vakit geçirmeden yapılması uygun olacaktır. Ayrıca toprak sıcaklığı eğilimleri mevsimsel sıcaklık dalgalanmaları, su kıtlığı, sulama talepleri ve ürün rotasyonu gibi öngörülen çeşitli çevresel sorunların azaltılmasını teşvik etmek için kullanılabilirler.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Trakya Yarımadası, Toprak, Sıcaklık, Trend, Analiz.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil is a natural cover in which the material, which is loosened by the physical disintegration of the bedrock and partly as a result of chemical decomposition, is a living environment for plants and animals together with mineral and organic substances (Kantarıcı, 2000; Atalay, 2016; Mermut, 2021). Soil type, diameter of soil pores, water and air ratios in the soil, soil color, organic matter content, slope of the land surface, vegetative cover, solar radiation, and soil albedo are the major factors affecting soil temperature (Kantarıcı, 2000; Onwuka, 2016). Furthermore, solar radiation, heat energy resulting from chemical and microbiological events in the soil, and heat energy coming from the depths of the earth are the sources of soil temperature (Kantarıcı, 2000). With the heating of the soil during the daytime, a movement towards the air occurs and the heat is transferred upwards. At night, both the soil and the air on the soil surface cool down by conduction caused by the effect of cold air covering the surface (Atalay, 2016; Bolat 2023). Significant fluctuations in solar radiation reaching the soil surface during the day cause fluctuations in the temperature of the soil surface (Sarıyev & Acar, 2021). Changes in the temperature of the soil surface also affect the subsoil temperature. Temperature transfer is faster in the surface soil layers and slower in the lower soil layers. The daily progression of surface temperature in the soil layer varies between 25-75 cm (Atalay, 2016). In the process of soil cooling, heat loss from the upper soil layers is higher than from the deep soil layers (Ekberli & Gülser, 2020). In dry soils with low water content, heat movement is predominantly by conduction, while in wet soils, heat energy is also transported by the flow of water heated from one region to another region (Sarıyev & Acar, 2021).

Soil temperature is an agrometeorological factor that affects all physical, chemical, and biological processes occurring in the edaphic environment (Gülser & Ekberli, 2002; Öztekin et al., 2008; Araghia et al., 2017). Thus, all processes in the soil, like seed germination, plant growth, nutrient uptake and decomposition, water uptake, crop productivity, plant survival in the dry season, the activities of microorganisms, decomposition of organic matter, plant diseases, insect occurrence, carbon and nitrogen transformations in the soil, evapotranspiration rate, soil hydrology, etc., depend on temperature (Alli & Omofunmi, 2021; Sarıyev & Acar, 2021; Bolat, 2023). Heat exchange in soil layers significantly affects the physical properties of soil and soil formation (Ekberli & Gülser, 2020). Soil temperature is one of the parameters that determines the ecological diversity in the soil and is essential for crop production (Başyigit & Dinç, 2005; Islam et al., 2015). The increase in temperature and decrease in precipitation due to climate change is very important in terms of soil moisture and plant yield (Yılmaz & Boyraz Erdem, 2021). On the other hand, a comprehensive analysis of soil temperature trends is crucial for the management of sustainable agricultural systems, such as determining ideal sowing dates, mitigating the negative effects of temperature stress, and determining the confidence levels of irrigation treatment times and intervals (Araghia et al., 2017; Inik et al., 2022).

1.1. Study Area

The study area of this study is the Thracian Peninsula (Figure 1). The Thracian Peninsula, with a surface area of 23,854 km², is surrounded by the Bosphorus and the Marmara Sea from the east, the Marmara Sea, the Dardanelles, and the Aegean Sea from the south, Greece and Bulgaria from the west, and Bulgaria and the Black Sea from the north (Özşahin & Eroğlu, 2018a).

In the Thracian Peninsula, the lowest monthly mean temperature in January was 2.6 °C in Edirne, and the highest monthly mean temperature was 6.9 °C in Gökçeada (Table 1). The lowest and highest temperature averages in July and August are 22.8 °C (July) in Çorlu and 25.1 °C (July, August) in Çanakkale. Annual average air temperature values are 13.1 °C in Çorlu, 13.3 °C in Kırklareli, 13.4 °C in Lüleburgaz, 13.7 °C in Uzunköprü and Malkara, 13.8 °C in Edirne, 14.1 °C in Sarıyer and Tekirdağ, 14.2 °C in Kumköy and İpsala, 14.4 °C in Florya, 15.2 °C in Çanakkale and 15.5 °C in Gökçeada (Table 1, Figure 2).

According to De Martonne annual drought index formula (1923), Kumköy (I:32.7) and Sarıyer (I:34) are in the humid climate area, while Kırklareli (I:25.1), Edirne (I:25.3), Lüleburgaz (I:25.9), Uzunköprü (I:28.1), Çorlu (I:25), Florya (I:26.2), Tekirdağ (I:24.1), İpsala (I:25.2), Malkara (I:28.2), Gökçeada (I:28.9) and Çanakkale (I:24.8) are in the semi-humid climate area (Ardel et al., 1965).

The fact that a statistically significant and positive increasing trend in minimum, maximum, and average air temperatures has been detected in the Thracian Peninsula is quite important in terms of showing the effects of global warming (Türkeş, 2012; Eroğlu, 2022; Eroğlu, 2023). On the other hand, it causes attention to be turned to soil temperatures in terms of the effects of global warming in this area where agricultural activities are intensively carried out, and the agricultural sector constitutes an important source

of livelihood (Erođlu, 2021). Based on this idea, this study aims to determine the long-term average soil temperatures at depths of 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm based on meteorological stations in the Thracian Peninsula in line with the principles of geography and to reveal whether there is a statistically significant trend in these soil temperatures. Undoubtedly, determination, monitoring, and changing trends of soil temperatures are both important and ecologically and economically necessary in terms of agricultural activities and crops grown.

This study used the data of 13 meteorological stations to determine the monthly and annual average soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths in the Thracian Peninsula and compared them with the average air temperatures. At the same time, the Mann-Kendall test was used to analyze whether there is an increasing or decreasing trend in the annual average soil temperatures. In this context, the effects of global climate change and global warming on soil temperatures at different depths in the Thracian Peninsula were tried to be determined.

Figure 1. Location Map of The Thracian Peninsula.

Table 1. Monthly and Annual Average Air Temperature Values in The Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1959-2022)	2.9	4.1	6.9	12.0	17.1	21.4	23.8	23.6	19.3	14.0	9.2	5.1	13.3
Edirne (1952-2022)	2.6	4.5	7.6	12.8	18.0	22.2	24.6	24.5	20.1	14.3	9.1	4.6	13.8
Lüleburgaz (1955-2022)	3.4	4.7	7.1	11.8	16.9	21.2	23.5	23.3	19.2	14.1	9.4	5.4	13.4
Uzunköprü (1965-2022)	2.9	4.6	7.7	12.4	17.6	22.0	24.4	24.2	20.0	14.4	9.4	5.0	13.7
Kumköy (1951-2022)	6.0	6.1	7.4	11.1	15.7	20.4	23.2	23.6	20.2	16.0	11.9	8.3	14.2
Çorlu (1958-2022)	3.4	4.1	6.5	11.2	16.3	20.6	22.8	22.6	19.0	14.2	9.8	5.7	13.1
Sarıyer (1954-2022)	5.7	5.8	7.3	11.2	15.8	20.5	23.0	23.3	20.0	15.9	11.7	8.0	14.1
Florya (1937-2022)	5.7	5.8	7.4	11.6	16.5	21.1	23.8	23.9	20.4	16.0	11.9	8.1	14.4
Tekirdağ (1940-2022)	4.8	5.5	7.3	11.8	16.7	21.1	23.7	23.9	20.2	15.6	11.3	7.2	14.1
İpsala (1964-2022)	3.9	5.4	8.0	12.8	17.9	22.4	24.7	24.4	20.1	14.7	10.0	5.9	14.2
Malkara (1980-2022)	3.7	4.5	7.3	12.0	16.9	21.5	23.8	23.9	19.9	14.6	9.6	5.6	13.7
Gökçeada (1965-2022)	6.9	7.3	9.2	13.4	17.9	22.5	24.8	24.6	21.1	16.3	12.3	8.8	15.5
Çanakkale (1937-2022)	6.2	6.8	8.4	12.6	17.5	22.2	25.1	25.1	21.1	16.3	12.1	8.4	15.2

(Source: T.C. Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, General Directorate of Meteorology).

Figure 2. Graph of Annual Average Air Temperature Values in The Thracian Peninsula.

2. MATERIAL and METHOD

Soil and air temperature data for the study area consist of 34-year (1990-2023) monthly and annual average soil temperatures measured at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths at the Kırklareli, Edirne, Lüleburgaz, Uzunköprü, Kumköy, Çorlu, Sarıyer, Florya, Tekirdağ, İpsala, Malkara, Gökçeada, and Çanakkale meteorological stations of the General Directorate of Meteorology of the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change (Table 2). Of these data sets, the measurement data of Kumköy meteorological station at 50 cm and 100 cm depths cover the period between 2005 and 2023 (19 years), and the measurement data of Sarıyer meteorological station at 50 cm and 100 cm depths cover the period between 2007 and 2023 (17 years). It was also deemed appropriate to utilize the long-term measurement values of Çanakkale (17112) and Gökçeada (17110) meteorological stations to make comparisons with previous studies in terms of both subject and area.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques were utilized for drawing the maps used in the study. The ArcGIS 10.8 program was used for this purpose. Soil temperature maps were drawn using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) method (Kömüşçü, 2024) according to the annual average soil temperature values of meteorological stations at different depths.

Table 2. Meteorological Stations Used in the Research Area and Their Characteristics.

Meteorology Station	Meteorology Station Number	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Soil Temperature Observation Years	Data Length (Years)	Air Temperature Observation Years	Data Length (Years)
Kırklareli	17052	41.7382 N	27.2178 E	232	1990-2023	34	1959-2023	65
Edirne	17050	41.6767 N	26.5508 E	51	1990-2023	34	1952-2023	72
Lüleburgaz	17631	41.3513 N	27.3108 E	46	1990-2023	34	1955-2023	69
Uzunköprü	17608	41.2726 N	26.7056 E	45	1990-2023	34	1965-2023	59
Kumköy	17059	41.2505 N	29.0384 E	38	1990-2023	34	1951-2023	73
Çorlu	17054	41.1798 N	27.8160 E	145	1990-2023	34	1958-2023	66
Sarıyer	17061	41.1464 N	29.0502 E	59	1990-2023	34	1954-2023	67
Florya	17636	40.9758 N	28.7865 E	37	1990-2023	34	1937-2023	87
Tekirdağ	17056	40.9585 N	27.4965 E	4	1990-2023	34	1940-2023	84
İpsala	17632	40.8900 N	26.3900 E	81	1990-2023	34	1964-2023	60
Malkara	17634	40.8873 N	26.9080 E	207	1990-2023	34	1980-2023	44
Gökçeada	17110	40.1910 N	25.9075 E	79	1990-2023	34	1965-2023	59
Çanakkale	17112	40.1410 N	26.3993 E	6	1990-2023	34	1937-2023	87

(Source: T.C. Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, General Directorate of Meteorology)

Pettitt's Test (Pettitt, 1979), Standard Normal Homogeneity Test (Alexandersson, 1986), Buishand's Test (Buishand, 1982), and Von Neumann's Test (Von Neumann, 1941) were applied for homogeneity tests of the data sets at a 99% confidence interval (Table 3). The XLSTAT (2024) package program was used to apply homogeneity tests to the data sets (URL 1). The results of the homogeneity tests (Wijngaard et al., 2003; Kocaoğlu & Çağlıyan, 2022) indicate that the soil temperature data of Kırklareli, Kumköy, and Florya weather stations are generally in class 1 and class 2 categories, the soil temperature data of Malkara weather station are all in class 3 category, and the soil temperature data of the remaining weather stations are generally in class 2 and class 3 categories (Table 3).

Table 3. Annual Average Soil Temperature Homogeneity Tests Values.

Meteorology Station	Soil Depth	Pettitt's Test P-Value	(SNHT) P-Value	Buishand's Test P-Value	Von Neumann's Test P-Value
Kırklareli	5 cm	0,188	0,024	0,264	0,006
	10 cm	0,343	0,030	0,107	0,035
	20 cm	0,060	0,002	0,004	0,001
	50 cm	0,097	0,007	0,085	0,008
	100 cm	0,613	0,339	0,190	0,010
Edime	5 cm	0,037	0,003	0,009	0,004
	10 cm	0,231	0,170	0,132	0,002
	20 cm	0,002	0,000	0,001	0,000
	50 cm	0,007	0,023	0,003	0,001
	100 cm	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
Lüleburgaz	5 cm	0,146	0,009	0,062	0,208
	10 cm	0,007	0,001	0,004	0,010
	20 cm	0,018	0,657	0,707	0,809
	50 cm	0,516	0,001	0,001	0,002
	100 cm	0,007	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
Uzunköprü	5 cm	0,031	0,011	0,014	0,001
	10 cm	0,049	0,003	0,008	0,002
	20 cm	0,038	0,002	0,008	0,004
	50 cm	0,065	0,003	0,008	0,009
	100 cm	0,018	0,001	0,005	0,004
Kumköy	5 cm	0,022	0,002	0,010	0,004
	10 cm	0,380	0,196	0,249	0,025
	20 cm	0,524	0,387	0,557	0,092
	50 cm	0,505	0,208	0,262	0,182
	100 cm	0,483	0,306	0,391	0,164
Çorlu	5 cm	0,047	0,047	0,021	0,281
	10 cm	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,001
	20 cm	0,008	0,005	0,004	0,000
	50 cm	0,003	0,006	0,003	0,000
	100 cm	0,003	0,003	0,001	0,010
Sarıyer	5 cm	0,788	0,192	0,292	0,022
	10 cm	0,631	0,002	0,012	<0,0001
	20 cm	0,504	0,006	0,006	0,008
	50 cm	0,085	0,017	0,047	0,015
	100 cm	0,770	0,402	0,482	0,132
Florya	5 cm	0,159	0,090	0,072	0,002
	10 cm	0,892	0,073	0,380	0,013
	20 cm	0,892	0,035	0,357	0,001
	50 cm	0,214	0,137	0,137	<0,0001
	100 cm	0,128	0,433	0,216	0,049
Tekirdağ	5 cm	0,990	0,734	0,573	0,109
	10 cm	0,001	<0,0001	0,002	0,007
	20 cm	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
	50 cm	0,000	0,001	0,000	<0,0001
	100 cm	0,001	0,001	0,000	0,001
İpsala	5 cm	0,139	0,056	0,076	<0,0001
	10 cm	<0,0001	0,000	0,000	<0,0001
	20 cm	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
	50 cm	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	0,000
	100 cm	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
Malkara	5 cm	0,007	<0,0001	0,000	0,000
	10 cm	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,001
	20 cm	0,000	<0,0001	0,000	<0,0001
	50 cm	0,006	0,000	0,001	0,001
	100 cm	0,000	<0,0001	<0,0001	0,000
Gökçeada	5 cm	0,090	0,063	0,083	0,033
	10 cm	<0,0001	0,001	<0,0001	0,000
	20 cm	0,034	0,088	0,020	0,021
	50 cm	0,084	0,019	0,034	0,006
	100 cm	0,033	<0,0001	0,026	<0,0001
Çanakkale	5 cm	0,367	0,223	0,198	0,025
	10 cm	0,036	0,004	0,009	0,025
	20 cm	0,005	0,000	0,001	0,000
	50 cm	0,031	0,008	0,018	0,011
	100 cm	0,001	<0,0001	0,000	0,000

Many parametric and nonparametric statistical tests are used to detect trends in time series. However, nonparametric tests are more useful in many time series, especially in hydrology and climatology (Araghia, et al., 2017). The Mann-Kendall test (Mann, 1945) is a rank-based nonparametric test widely used in climatological studies to detect trends in time series (Partal, 2003; Nalley et al., 2013). Mann-Kendall (Mann, 1945; Hirsch & Slack, 1984), Kendall's Tau, and Sen's Slope (Sen, 1968) tests were used for trend analysis of time series of annual mean soil temperatures at different depths. The Mann-Kendall test, known

as the most useful method for trend analysis of data series, is based on the order, not the magnitude, of consecutive data (Burn & Elnur, 2002). In this test, trend analysis of soil temperatures was statistically evaluated at the $\alpha=0.05$ significance level and 95% confidence interval. A positive value in Sen's Slope Test indicates an increasing trend, while a negative trend shows a decreasing trend (Kocaoğlu & Çağlıyan, 2022). The following equation is used in the Mann-Kendall test statistic (Yu et al., 1993; Partal, 2003; Rahman & Dawood, 2017; Terzi & İlker, 2021):

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{Sgn}(X_j - X_k) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{sgn}(X_j - X_k) = \begin{cases} (X_j - X_k) > 0 \Rightarrow +1 \\ (X_j - X_k) = 0 \Rightarrow 0 \\ (X_j - X_k) < 0 \Rightarrow -1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_i^r t_i(t_i-1)(2t_i+5)}{18} \quad (4)$$

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{[\text{Var}(S)]^{\frac{1}{2}}} & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{[\text{Var}(S)]^{\frac{1}{2}}} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Sen's Trend Test is a nonparametric trend test proposed by Hirsch (1984) and developed by Sen (1968) (Hirsch, 1984; Sen, 1968). The following equation is used in this test, which is not affected by data errors and extreme values (Partal & Kahya, 2006; Rahman & Dawood, 2017).

$$Q_i = \frac{X_j - X_k}{j - k}$$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Average Soil Temperatures

An examination of monthly and annual average soil temperatures at 5 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula shows that the lowest monthly average values are observed in January and the highest monthly average values are observed in July and August (Table 4, Figure 3). The lowest monthly average soil temperature at 5 cm depth in January was 2.8 °C in Edirne, and the highest monthly average soil temperature was 6.7 °C in Çanakkale. In July and August, the lowest monthly mean values were 27.1 °C in Kumköy (July) and Sarıyer (August) and the highest monthly mean soil temperature was 30 °C in Çanakkale (July). At 5 cm depth, annual average soil temperatures ranged from 15.4 °C in Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, and Çorlu; 15.7 °C in Sarıyer; 15.8 °C in Malkara; 15.9 °C in Edirne; 16 °C in Kumköy; 16.1 °C in Uzunköprü and Florya; 16.2 °C in İpsala; 17 °C in Tekirdağ; 17.1 °C in Gökçeada; and 17.7 °C in Çanakkale.

In the Thracian Peninsula, the average soil temperature at 5 cm depth varied between 2.8 °C (Edirne) and 6.7 °C (Çanakkale) in January, while the average air temperature varied between 2.6 °C (Edirne) and 6.9 °C (Gökçeada) in January (Table 1, Table 4, Figure 8). At 5 cm depth, the average soil temperature was 27.1 °C (Kumköy, July and Sarıyer, August) and 30 °C (Çanakkale, July) in July and August, respectively. The average air temperature during these months varies between 22.6 °C (Çorlu, August) and 25.1 °C (Çanakkale, July and August). At 5 cm depth, annual average soil temperatures range between 15.4 °C (Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.7 °C (Gökçeada, Çanakkale), while annual average air temperatures range between 13.1 °C (Çorlu) and 15.5 °C (Gökçeada). Therefore, the average soil and air temperatures at 5 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula are close to each other in January, while the average soil temperatures are 4 °C higher than the average air temperatures in July and August and more than 2 °C higher than the annual average temperatures.

Table 4. Average Soil Temperatures at 5 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1990-2023)	4.1	5.1	8.4	13.7	19.9	24.5	27.5	27.7	22.1	15.5	10.1	5.9	15.4
Edirne (1990-2023)	2.8	4.8	9.0	15.1	21.6	26.4	29.2	29.1	23.3	15.6	9.2	4.5	15.9
Lüleburgaz (1990-2023)	4.2	5.0	8.0	13.0	19.4	24.4	27.6	27.7	22.6	16.1	10.3	6.1	15.4
Uzunköprü (1990-2023)	4.5	5.7	9.1	14.1	20.5	25.3	28.3	28.4	23.4	16.8	11.0	6.3	16.1
Kumköy (1990-2023)	6.3	6.5	8.7	12.9	18.5	23.7	27.1	27.4	22.8	17.5	12.4	8.2	16.0
Çorlu (1990-2023)	3.9	4.8	7.9	13.7	20.1	25.0	27.7	27.6	22.3	15.8	10.1	5.6	15.4
Sarıyer (1990-2023)	5.7	6.0	8.4	12.9	18.8	24.1	27.3	27.1	21.9	16.6	11.6	7.6	15.7
Florya (1990-2023)	5.9	6.3	8.9	14.0	20.0	25.0	27.9	27.2	22.2	16.7	11.7	7.8	16.1
Tekirdağ (1990-2023)	5.4	6.2	9.3	14.7	21.2	26.4	29.7	29.5	24.3	17.5	11.9	7.3	17.0
İpsala (1990-2023)	4.5	6.0	8.9	14.2	20.7	25.9	28.7	28.4	23.3	16.3	10.8	6.2	16.2
Malkara (1990-2023)	4.6	5.5	8.5	13.5	19.8	25.1	28.1	28.3	23.0	16.4	10.7	6.3	15.8
Gökçeada (1990-2023)	6.4	6.9	9.4	14.1	20.6	26.2	29.4	29.3	24.3	17.6	12.3	8.2	17.1
Çanakkale (1990-2023)	6.7	7.3	10.1	15.2	21.6	27.0	30.0	29.8	24.7	18.3	12.9	8.5	17.7

Figure 3. Distribution Map of Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 5 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

In the Thracian Peninsula, monthly mean soil temperatures at 10 cm depth ranged from 3.1 °C (Edirne) to 7.1 °C (Gökçeada) as the lowest, in January, and 26.3 °C (August, Florya) to 29.6 °C (July and August, Gökçeada) as the highest, in July and August (Table 5, Figure 4). At 10 cm depth, the annual average soil temperatures were between 15.4 °C and 17.7 °C, as at 5 cm depth. At 10 cm depth, the annual mean soil temperatures were 15.4 °C in Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, and Çorlu; 15.7 °C in Sarıyer; 15.8 °C in Malkara; 16 °C in Edirne and Florya; 16.2 °C in Uzunköprü; 16.3 °C in İpsala; 16.4 °C in Kumköy; 17.1 °C in Tekirdağ; 17.6 °C in Çanakkale; and 17.7 °C in Gökçeada.

In the Thracian Peninsula, the average soil temperature at 10 cm depth ranged between 3.1 °C (Edirne) and 7.1 °C (Gökçeada) in January, while the average air temperature ranged between 2.6 °C (Edirne) and 6.9 °C (Gökçeada) in January (Table 1, Table 5, Figure 8). The average soil temperature during the summer months between 26.3 °C (Florya, August) and 29.6 °C (Gökçeada, July and August) is higher than the average air temperature, which is between 22.6 °C (Çorlu, August) and 25.1 °C (Çanakkale, July and August). On the other hand, average soil temperatures between 15.4 °C (Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.7 °C (Gökçeada) are also higher than the annual average air temperatures, which are between 13.1 °C (Çorlu) and 15.5 °C (Gökçeada). From these average values, it is understood that average soil temperatures at 10 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula are 0.2 °C to 0.5 °C higher in January, 3.7 °C to 4.5 °C higher in July and August, and 2.2 °C to 2.3 °C higher in annual averages compared to average air temperatures. On the other hand, it was found that there were strong relationships between soil temperatures at 5 cm and 10

cm soil depths and climate parameters such as daily temperature, daily above-ground minimum temperature, radiation data, wind speed, precipitation, and relative humidity (Öztekin et al., 2008).

Table 5. Average Soil Temperatures at 10 cm Depth in the Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1990-2023)	4.4	5.1	8.4	13.6	19.6	24.0	27.0	27.4	22.1	15.7	10.4	6.1	15.4
Edirne (1990-2023)	3.1	4.8	8.7	14.7	21.0	25.8	28.6	28.6	23.1	15.6	9.2	4.7	16.0
Lüleburgaz (1990-2023)	4.4	5.1	7.9	12.8	19.1	24.1	27.3	27.4	22.6	16.2	10.5	6.3	15.4
Uzunköprü (1990-2023)	4.9	6.0	9.1	14.1	20.2	24.8	27.9	28.1	23.5	17.2	11.5	6.9	16.2
Kumköy (1990-2023)	6.7	6.8	8.9	12.9	18.2	23.7	27.1	27.3	22.8	17.6	12.8	8.8	16.4
Çorlu (1990-2023)	4.2	4.9	7.9	13.3	19.6	24.4	27.2	27.2	22.4	16.2	10.5	6.1	15.4
Sarıyer (1990-2023)	6.0	6.2	8.5	12.8	18.5	23.7	26.8	26.9	22.1	16.9	12.0	7.9	15.7
Florya (1990-2023)	6.4	6.6	8.9	13.5	19.1	24.1	26.8	26.3	22.1	17.1	12.0	8.3	16.0
Tekirdağ (1990-2023)	5.7	6.4	9.4	14.7	21.0	26.1	29.3	29.3	24.4	17.9	12.3	7.7	17.1
İpsala (1990-2023)	5.0	6.3	9.2	14.0	20.2	25.1	28.1	27.9	23.2	16.8	11.3	6.8	16.3
Malkara (1990-2023)	4.9	5.6	8.4	13.3	19.5	24.6	27.6	27.9	23.0	16.6	10.9	6.6	15.8
Gökçeada (1990-2023)	7.1	7.5	10.0	14.6	20.8	26.2	29.6	29.6	25.1	18.6	13.3	9.1	17.7
Çanakkale (1990-2023)	7.0	7.5	10.1	14.9	21.0	26.1	29.1	29.0	24.6	18.5	13.3	9.0	17.6

Figure 4. Distribution Map of the Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 10 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

In the Thracian Peninsula, the lowest monthly average soil temperature at 20 cm depth was observed in Edirne with 3.3 °C in January (Table 6, Figure 5). Soil temperature was 4.5 °C in Çorlu, 4.6 °C in Lüleburgaz, 4.8 °C in Kırklareli, 5.4 °C in Uzunköprü, İpsala, and Malkara, 6.2 °C in Tekirdağ, 6.4 °C in Sarıyer, 6.7 °C in Florya, 7.2 °C in Kumköy, 7.4 °C in Gökçeada, and 7.6 °C in Çanakkale. The highest monthly average soil temperatures at 20 cm depth during the summer season were in August at all meteorological stations except Ipsala (27.3 °C in July) and Florya (26.1 °C in July, 26.1 °C in August). Average soil temperatures in this month are 26.2 °C in Sarıyer, 26.7 °C in Çorlu, 26.8 °C in Kırklareli, 27.1 °C in Kumköy and Lüleburgaz, 27.3 °C in Malkara, 27.6 °C in Uzunköprü, 28.2 °C in Çanakkale, 28.3 °C in Edirne, 28.7 °C in Tekirdağ and 29.1 °C in Gökçeada. In the Thracian Peninsula, annual average soil temperatures at 20 cm depth range between 15.3 °C (Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.5 °C (Gökçeada).

An examination of the average soil and air temperatures in January at a depth of 20 cm in the Thracian Peninsula reveals that the soil temperature averages showed higher values (Table 1, Table 6, Figure 8). The lowest average soil (3.3 °C) and air (2.6 °C) temperatures were recorded in Edirne, the highest average soil temperature was recorded in Çanakkale (7.6 °C), and the highest average air temperature was recorded in Gökçeada (6.9 °C). At 20 cm depth, the difference between January average soil and air temperatures is 0.7 °C. In summer, the temperature difference between the lowest average soil and air temperatures at 20 cm

depth is 3.3 °C (26.1 °C in Florya in July, August, and 22.8 °C in Çorlu in July), and between the highest average soil and average air temperatures is 4 °C (29.1 °C in Gökçeada in August, 25.1 °C in Çanakkale in July, August). The lowest average annual soil temperature was 15.3 °C in Lüleburgaz and Çorlu; the lowest average air temperature was 13.1 °C in Çorlu with a difference of 2.2 °C; the highest soil temperature was 17.5 °C in Gökçeada, and the highest air temperature was 15.5 °C in Gökçeada with a difference of 2 °C.

Table 6. Average Soil Temperatures at 20 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1990-2023)	4.8	5.5	8.4	13.2	19.0	23.4	26.4	26.8	22.2	16.1	11.0	6.8	15.4
Edirne (1990-2023)	3.3	4.8	8.7	14.3	20.4	25.2	28.1	28.3	23.5	16.3	10.1	5.3	15.8
Lüleburgaz (1990-2023)	4.6	5.2	8.0	12.7	18.9	23.7	26.9	27.1	22.5	16.1	10.4	6.7	15.3
Uzunköprü (1990-2023)	5.4	6.2	9.1	13.7	19.5	24.1	27.1	27.6	23.6	17.6	12.2	7.5	16.1
Kumköy (1990-2023)	7.2	7.2	9.0	12.7	18.0	23.1	26.6	27.1	23.2	18.4	13.4	9.5	16.5
Çorlu (1990-2023)	4.5	5.0	7.7	12.8	18.8	23.6	26.6	26.7	22.4	16.6	11.0	6.5	15.3
Sarıyer (1990-2023)	6.4	6.4	8.5	12.3	17.5	22.4	25.8	26.2	21.8	17.0	12.5	8.5	15.4
Florya (1990-2023)	6.7	6.7	8.9	13.3	18.7	23.4	26.1	26.1	22.3	17.5	12.7	8.8	16.0
Tekirdağ (1990-2023)	6.2	6.7	9.4	14.3	20.2	25.2	28.4	28.7	24.4	18.4	12.9	8.3	16.9
İpsala (1990-2023)	5.4	6.3	9.0	13.3	19.3	24.1	27.3	27.2	23.2	17.2	11.9	7.4	16.0
Malkara (1990-2023)	5.4	5.9	8.5	13.0	18.7	23.7	26.8	27.3	23.1	17.2	11.7	7.4	15.8
Gökçeada (1990-2023)	7.4	7.5	9.8	14.1	20.1	25.4	28.9	29.1	25.1	18.9	13.6	9.5	17.5
Çanakkale (1990-2023)	7.6	7.8	10.1	14.5	20.2	25.1	27.9	28.2	24.6	19.1	13.9	9.7	17.4

Figure 5. Distribution Map of Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 20 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

The annual average soil temperatures at 50 cm depth in the Thrace Peninsula are around 15 °C in Çorlu (15.3 °C), Sarıyer (15.4 °C), Kırklareli (15.5 °C), Malkara (15.7 °C), and Edirne (15.9 °C) (Table 7, Figure 6). This value increases to 16 °C in Ipsala (16.1 °C), Uzunköprü (16.3 °C), Lüleburgaz (16.4 °C), Florya (16.5 °C), Tekirdağ (16.7 °C), and Kumköy (16.8 °C), and to 17 °C in Çanakkale (17.6 °C) and Gökçeada (17.7 °C). At 50 cm depth, the lowest soil temperatures are observed in January and February. The lowest soil temperatures in these months were 5 °C in Edirne (January), 5.6 °C in Çorlu (January, February), 6.7 °C in Kırklareli and Malkara (February), 7 °C in Uzunköprü (January), 7.2 °C (January, February), 7.3 °C (February) in Lüleburgaz (January, February) and Tekirdağ, 7.5 °C (February) in Sarıyer, 8.1 °C (February) in Florya, 8.3 °C (February) in Kumköy, 8.6 °C (February) in Gökçeada, and 9.2 °C (February) in Çanakkale. The highest monthly average soil temperatures at 50 cm depth are observed in August. The highest average temperature in August is 28.1 °C in Gökçeada, and the lowest average temperature is 24.7 °C in Sarıyer.

The comparison of the average soil and air temperatures in January at 50 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula shows that the lowest monthly average air temperatures in January were between 2.6 °C (Edirne) and 6.9 °C (Gökçeada), while the lowest soil temperatures were between 5 °C (Edirne) and 9.2 °C (Çanakkale) (Table 1, Table 7, Figure 8). The lowest soil temperature averages were observed in Edirne (5 °C) and Uzunköprü (7 °C) in January, Çorlu (5.6 °C), İpsala (7.2 °C), and Lüleburgaz (7.3 °C) in January and February, Kırklareli (6.7 °C), Malkara (6.7 °C), Tekirdağ (7.3 °C), Sarıyer (7.5 °C), Florya (8.1 °C), Kumköy (8.3 °C), Gökçeada (8.6 °C), and Çanakkale (9.2 °C) in February. Accordingly, in January and February, the soil at a depth of 50 cm is more than 2 °C warmer than the air above it (2.4 °C in the lowest averages and 2.3 °C in the highest averages). In summer, the lowest soil temperature was 24.7 °C in Sarıyer (August), and the lowest air temperature was 22.8 °C in Çorlu (July), with a difference of 1.9 °C. The highest soil temperature was 28.1 °C in Gökçeada (August), the highest air temperature was 25.1 °C in Çanakkale (July, August), and the difference was 3 °C. In annual average temperatures, soil temperature values at 50 cm depth are higher than air temperature values. In the Thracian Peninsula, the lowest annual mean soil (15.3 °C) and air (13.1 °C) temperatures at a depth of 50 cm belong to Çorlu, and the highest annual mean soil (17.7 °C) and air (15.5 °C) temperatures belong to Gökçeada. The temperature difference between the highest and lowest figures of soil and air temperatures in annual average temperatures is 2.2 °C.

Table 7. Average Soil Temperatures at 50 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1990-2023)	6.8	6.7	8.9	12.6	17.4	21.4	24.3	25.3	22.3	17.5	12.9	9.0	15.5
Edirne (1990-2023)	5.0	5.6	8.7	13.3	18.7	23.3	26.4	27.2	24.0	18.0	12.1	7.4	15.9
Lüleburgaz (1990-2023)	7.3	7.3	9.4	13.1	18.3	22.6	25.8	26.7	23.6	18.6	13.7	9.9	16.4
Uzunköprü (1990-2023)	7.0	7.1	9.3	13.0	18.0	22.4	25.7	26.6	24.0	18.9	13.8	9.3	16.3
Kumköy (2005-2023)	8.7	8.3	9.7	12.6	17.1	22.0	25.5	26.6	23.8	19.4	15.0	11.2	16.8
Çorlu (1990-2023)	5.6	5.6	7.7	12.0	17.5	22.1	25.3	26.0	22.8	17.7	12.4	7.9	15.3
Sarıyer (2007-2023)	7.8	7.5	8.8	11.6	15.9	20.3	23.6	24.7	22.4	17.9	14.1	10.2	15.4
Florya (1990-2023)	8.7	8.1	9.7	13.1	17.7	22.0	24.8	25.5	23.1	19.3	14.8	11.0	16.5
Tekirdağ (1990-2023)	7.4	7.3	9.2	13.3	18.5	23.1	26.5	27.3	24.4	19.2	14.2	9.8	16.7
İpsala (1990-2023)	7.2	7.2	9.2	12.7	17.5	22.0	25.3	26.1	23.3	18.5	13.6	9.5	16.1
Malkara (1990-2023)	6.8	6.7	8.6	12.2	17.1	21.7	25.0	26.0	23.1	18.2	13.2	9.1	15.7
Gökçeada (1990-2023)	9.0	8.6	10.2	13.6	18.6	23.7	27.3	28.1	25.4	20.4	15.4	11.4	17.7
Çanakkale (1990-2023)	9.6	9.2	10.6	13.9	18.6	22.9	25.9	26.8	24.6	20.5	16.1	12.0	17.6

Figure 6. Distribution Map of Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 50 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

In the Thracian Peninsula, the lowest values of the average soil temperatures at 100 cm depth are shifted to February in all meteorological stations. In this month, average soil temperatures ranged between 7 °C (Çorlu) and 10.9 °C (Çanakkale) (Table 8, Figure 7). The highest monthly mean values were measured between 22.9 °C (Kırklareli) and 26.3 °C (Gökçeada) in August. At 100 cm depth, annual average soil

temperatures were 15.2 °C in Sarıyer, 15.5 °C in Çorlu and Malkara, 15.6 °C in Kırklareli, 15.7 °C in Edirne, 15.9 °C in İpsala, 16.2 °C in Uzunköprü and Florya, 16.7 °C in Tekirdağ, 16.8 °C in Lüleburgaz, 16.9 °C in Kumköy, 17.6 °C in Çanakkale, and 17.6 °C in Gökçeada.

In the Thracian Peninsula, the difference between the average soil and air temperatures at a depth of 100 cm in winter exceeds 4 °C (Table 1, Table 8, Figure 8). In this season, the lowest average soil temperature at 100 cm depth was 7 °C in Çorlu, the lowest average air temperature was 2.6 °C in Edirne, the highest average soil temperature was 10.9 °C in Çanakkale, and the highest average air temperature was 6.9 °C in Gökçeada. In summer, air temperatures were slightly higher (0.1 °C at the lowest temperatures and 1.2 °C at the highest temperatures) than soil temperatures (Kırklareli 22.9 °C, Çorlu 22.8 °C, Gökçeada 26.3 °C, and Çanakkale 25.1 °C). In annual averages, soil temperatures at 100 cm depth are more than 2 °C warmer than air temperatures both in the lowest averages (15.2 °C Sarıyer, 13.1 °C Çorlu) and in the highest averages (17.8 °C Gökçeada, 15.5 °C Gökçeada).

Although air temperatures in the research area increased in February compared to January, the fact that the lowest average soil temperatures at a depth of 100 cm shifted to February indicates that the temperature in the lower layers of the soil is lower than the air temperature. On the other hand, the temperature transition is faster in the upper soil and slower in the lower soil layers (Atalay, 2016).

Table 8. Average Soil Temperatures at 100 cm Depth in the Thracian Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Kırklareli (1990-2023)	9.6	8.8	9.9	12.3	15.6	18.9	21.5	22.9	21.8	18.8	15.3	12.1	15.6
Edirne (1990-2023)	7.7	7.1	8.8	11.9	16.1	20.1	23.2	24.7	23.5	19.6	14.9	10.7	15.7
Lüleburgaz (1990-2023)	9.0	8.6	10.1	12.7	16.8	21.2	24.4	25.5	23.6	19.9	15.3	12.0	16.8
Uzunköprü (1990-2023)	9.0	8.3	9.6	12.3	16.2	20.1	23.4	24.9	23.6	19.9	15.7	11.7	16.2
Kumköy (2005-2023)	10.6	9.6	10.3	12.3	15.8	19.9	23.4	25.1	23.9	20.4	16.7	13.2	16.9
Çorlu (1990-2023)	7.7	7.0	8.2	11.3	15.8	20.0	23.4	24.8	23.1	19.2	14.6	10.4	15.5
Sarıyer (2007-2023)	9.1	8.2	9.0	11.1	14.6	18.4	21.6	23.2	22.1	18.6	15.3	11.8	15.2
Florya (1990-2023)	10.5	9.4	10.1	12.2	15.6	19.1	22.0	23.4	22.5	19.9	16.2	12.9	16.2
Tekirdağ (1990-2023)	9.5	8.7	9.8	12.5	16.5	20.6	24.0	25.5	24.2	20.4	16.2	12.3	16.7
İpsala (1990-2023)	9.7	8.8	9.7	11.9	15.3	19.1	22.2	23.6	22.6	19.6	15.8	12.4	15.9
Malkara (1990-2023)	9.1	8.3	9.1	11.4	14.9	18.6	21.8	23.4	22.4	19.3	15.4	11.7	15.5
Gökçeada (1990-2023)	11.3	10.2	10.9	13.1	16.7	21.0	24.6	26.3	25.3	21.8	17.7	14.0	17.8
Çanakkale (1990-2023)	11.9	10.9	11.5	13.4	16.7	20.2	23.1	24.7	24.1	21.5	18.0	14.4	17.6

Figure 7. Distribution Map of Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 100 cm Depth in The Thracian Peninsula.

Figure 8. Graph of the Difference between Annual Average Soil Temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm and 100 cm Depths and Annual Average Air Temperatures in The Thracian Peninsula.

3.2. Trend Analysis of Soil Temperatures

3.2.1. Trend Analysis of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures

The Mann-Kendall trend analysis values of monthly average soil temperatures at 5 cm depth in the Thrace Peninsula (Table 9) suggest that there is a statistically significant and positive trend in all meteorological stations except Sarıyer and Tekirdağ in November and December. There is a statistically significant and positive trend in all stations except Sarıyer, Florya, Tekirdağ, and İpsala in January and Uzunköprü, Sarıyer, and Tekirdağ in February. November, December, January, and February are also the months with the highest number of stations with significant increases in soil temperature. The trend direction of all stations with significant trends in April, May, June, and July is negative. There is a significant positive trend in Kırklareli, İpsala, and Malkara and a significant negative trend in Uzunköprü, Florya, Gökçeada, and Çanakkale in August.

Table 9. Trend Values of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures at 5 cm Depth in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Test Name	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Kırklareli	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Edirne	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Lüleburgaz	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Uzunköprü	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
Kumköy	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çorlu	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
Sarıyer	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
Florya	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
Tekirdağ	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
İpsala	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Malkara	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Gökçeada	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Çanakkale	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

At 10 cm depth, monthly mean soil temperatures in January, February, March, September, October, November, and December showed a significant trend in all stations (Table 10). The trend direction is negative in Kırklareli, Edirne, Florya, and Gökçeada, where there is a significant trend in June. August, September, November, December, January, and February are the months with the highest number of stations with significant positive trends. In other words, in these months, soil temperatures at 10 cm depth in the research area tend to increase. In April and May, no trend is detected in any of the stations in the field.

Table 10. Trend Values of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures at 10 cm Depth in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Test Name	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Kırklareli	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Edirne	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Lüleburgaz	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Uzunköprü	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
Kumköy	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çorlu	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
Sarıyer	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
Florya	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
Tekirdağ	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
İpsala	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Malkara	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Gökçeada	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çanakkale	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

Monthly average soil temperatures at 20 cm depth show a positive and significant trend at six stations in August, seven stations in September, eleven stations in November, nine stations in December, eight stations in January, and nine stations in February (Table 11). There is a significant and positive trend in Malkara and Çanakkale in March and only in Lüleburgaz in October. At 20 cm depth, significant negative

trends in monthly soil temperatures are tested at Gökçeada in May; Kırklareli, Florya, and Gökçeada in June; and Florya in July and August. There is no significant trend in soil temperatures at any station in the field in April.

Table 11. Trend Values of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures at 20 cm Depth in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Test Name	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Kırklareli	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Edirne	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Lüleburgaz	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Uzunköprü	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Kumköy	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
Çorlu	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
Sarıyer	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓
Florya	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Tekirdağ	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
İpsala	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Malkara	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Gökçeada	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çanakkale	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

The number of stations with significant positive trends in monthly average soil temperatures at 50 cm depth is higher in August, September, November, December, and February than in other months (Table 12). A significant positive trend is observed only in Malkara in March, while there is no significant trend in April at any station in the field. In May, there is a significant positive trend in Tekirdağ and a significant negative trend in Gökçeada. In June, the stations with a significant negative trend are Kırklareli, Florya, and Gökçeada, and the station with a significant positive trend is Tekirdağ. In July, the stations with a significant positive trend are Tekirdağ, İpsala, and Çanakkale, and the station with a significant negative

trend is Florya. In October, Kırklareli and İpsala are the stations with a significant positive trend in monthly average soil temperature at 50 cm depth.

Table 12. Trend Values of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures at 50 cm Depth in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Test Name	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Kırklareli	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Edirne	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Lüleburgaz	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓
Uzunköprü	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Kumköy	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓
Çorlu	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑
Sarıyer	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Florya	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
Tekirdağ	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
İpsala	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Malkara	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Gökçeada	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çanakkale	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

Monthly mean soil temperatures at 100 cm depth have significant and positive trends in eleven months of the year in Edirne and Çanakkale stations (except April) and in ten months of the year in Malkara (except June and July) and Gökçeada (except May and June) (Table 13). After these stations, Uzunköprü (8 months) and İpsala (7 months) are the centers with the most significant and positive trends in monthly average soil temperatures at 100 cm depth during the year. In Kırklareli, soil temperature shows a negative and significant trend in the three months between April and June, while it shows a positive and significant trend in the four months between August and November. Lüleburgaz differs from the other stations in that it is the station with a negative and significant trend in soil temperatures at 100 cm depth in the six months between February and July.

Table 13. Trend Values of Monthly Average Soil Temperatures at 100 cm Depth in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Test Name	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Kırklareli	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Edirne	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Lüleburgaz	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓
Uzunköprü	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Kumköy	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Çorlu	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Sarıyer	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Florya	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑
Tekirdağ	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓
	Sen's Slope	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓
İpsala	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Malkara	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Gökçeada	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Çanakkale	Mann-Kendall	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲
	Kendall's Tau	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Sen's Slope	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

3.2.2. Trend Analysis of Annual Average Soil Temperatures

There is a positive and statistically significant trend in Lüleburgaz, Çorlu, and Malkara and a negative and statistically significant trend in Florya, according to the significance level of $p=0.05$ for the annual average soil temperature values at 5 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula (Table 14). There is a positive and insignificant trend in Kırklareli, Edirne, Kumköy, Sarıyer, and İpsala; a negative and insignificant trend in Uzunköprü, Gökçeada, and Çanakkale; a negative and insignificant trend in Tekirdağ according to Kendall's Tau test; and a positive and insignificant trend according to Sen's slope test.

Annual mean soil temperature values at 10 cm depth show a positive and significant trend in Lüleburgaz, Çorlu, Tekirdağ, İpsala, Malkara, and Gökçeada meteorological stations. On the contrary, there is a positive insignificant trend in Kırklareli, Uzunköprü, Kumköy, Florya, and Çanakkale and a negative insignificant trend in Edirne and Sarıyer meteorological stations.

It is determined that the number of stations with a significant positive trend in annual average soil temperatures at 20 cm depth is increasing in the Thracian Peninsula. There is a positive and significant trend at Kırklareli, Edirne, Lüleburgaz, Uzunköprü, Çorlu, Tekirdağ, İpsala, Malkara, Gökçeada, and Çanakkale stations. A positive but statistically insignificant trend is detected at Kumköy, Sarıyer, and Florya stations.

In the research area, the stations with a significant and positive trend in annual mean soil temperatures at 50 cm depth are Kırklareli, Edirne, Uzunköprü, Çorlu, Tekirdağ, İpsala, Malkara, and Çanakkale. Lüleburgaz, Kumköy, Sarıyer, and Florya have a statistically insignificant and at the same time negative trend, while Gökçeada has an insignificant but positive trend, unlike the other stations.

The annual average soil temperatures at 100 cm depth have a significant trend at Edirne, Uzunköprü, Çorlu, Tekirdağ, İpsala, Malkara, Gökçeada, and Çanakkale meteorological stations according to the Mann-Kendall test and an insignificant trend at Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, Kumköy, Sarıyer, and Florya meteorological stations. In all of the stations with a statistically significant trend, the trend direction is positive according to Kendall's Tau and Sen's slope tests. According to Kendall's Tau and Sen's Slope tests, the trend direction is positive at Kırklareli and Florya and negative at Lüleburgaz, Kumköy, and Sarıyer (Table 14).

Of the meteorological stations in the Thracian Peninsula, Çorlu and Malkara show a significant and positive trend in all annual average soil temperatures at depths of 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm, while Kumköy and Sarıyer show a negative trend in all annual average soil temperatures at these depths. Florya is the only station where the annual mean soil temperature at 5 cm depth shows a significant trend. A statistically significant trend in the annual average soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, and 20 cm depths and a trend in the direction of temperature increase is determined in Lüleburgaz. Gökçeada is the station with a significant trend at 10 cm and 20 cm depths; Tekirdağ and İpsala are the stations with a significant trend at 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths; Kırklareli is the station with a significant trend at 20 cm and 50 cm depths; and Edirne, Uzunköprü, and Çanakkale are the stations with a significant trend at 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths.

Table 14. Trend Values of Annual Mean Soil Temperatures at 5 cm, 10cm, 20 cm, 50 cm and 100 cm Depths in Thrace Peninsula.

Meteorology Station	Soil Depth	Mann-Kendall P (Value) ($\alpha=0,05$)		Kendall's Tau		Sen's Slope	
Kırklareli	5 cm	0,100	▲	0,206	↑	0,029	↑
	10 cm	0,132	▲	0,189	↑	0,017	↑
	20 cm	0,006	▲	0,341	↑	0,038	↑
	50 cm	0,013	▲	0,311	↑	0,025	↑
	100 cm	0,651	▲	0,059	↑	0,000	↑
Edirne	5 cm	0,100	▲	0,206	↑	0,020	↑
	10 cm	0,208	▲	-0,158	↓	-0,017	↓
	20 cm	0,003	▲	0,365	↑	0,046	↑
	50 cm	0,008	▲	0,334	↑	0,041	↑
	100 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,517	↑	0,064	↑
Lüleburgaz	5 cm	0,045	▲	0,251	↑	0,029	↑
	10 cm	0,000	▲	0,435	↑	0,052	↑
	20 cm	0,001	▲	0,409	↑	0,050	↑
	50 cm	0,641	▲	-0,060	↓	-0,006	↓
	100 cm	0,238	▲	-0,147	↓	-0,031	↓
Uzunköprü	5 cm	0,313	▲	-0,127	↓	-0,020	↓
	10 cm	0,074	▲	0,224	↑	0,028	↑
	20 cm	0,023	▲	0,284	↑	0,033	↑
	50 cm	0,048	▲	0,247	↑	0,030	↑
	100 cm	0,003	▲	0,372	↑	0,040	↑
Kumköy	5 cm	0,178	▲	0,171	↑	0,032	↑
	10 cm	0,182	▲	0,171	↑	0,019	↑
	20 cm	0,262	▲	0,144	↑	0,019	↑
	50 cm	0,802	▲	-0,052	↓	-0,019	↓
	100 cm	0,804	▲	-0,052	↓	-0,018	↓

Table 14. Trend Values of Annual Mean Soil Temperatures at 5 cm, 10cm, 20 cm, 50 cm and 100 cm Depths in Thrace Peninsula (*Cont.*).

Meteorology Station	Soil Depth	Mann-Kendall P (Value) ($\alpha=0,05$)		Kendall's Tau		Sen's Slope	
Çorlu	5 cm	0,048	▲	0,248	↑	0,024	↑
	10 cm	0,001	▲	0,407	↑	0,039	↑
	20 cm	0,014	▲	0,307	↑	0,038	↑
	50 cm	0,017	▲	0,298	↑	0,032	↑
	100 cm	0,016	▲	0,301	↑	0,033	↑
Sarıyer	5 cm	0,686	▲	0,052	↑	0,007	↑
	10 cm	0,935	▲	-0,012	↓	0,000	↓
	20 cm	0,832	▲	0,029	↑	0,000	↑
	50 cm	0,175	▲	-0,262	↓	-0,062	↓
	100 cm	0,807	▲	-0,065	↓	-0,025	↓
Florya	5 cm	0,035	▲	-0,265	↓	-0,033	↓
	10 cm	0,815	▲	0,031	↑	0,000	↑
	20 cm	0,756	▲	0,041	↑	0,000	↑
	50 cm	0,733	▲	-0,044	↓	-0,007	↓
	100 cm	0,475	▲	0,090	↑	0,012	↑
Tekirdağ	5 cm	0,975	▲	-0,006	↓	0,000	↑
	10 cm	0,001	▲	0,418	↑	0,036	↑
	20 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,548	↑	0,064	↑
	50 cm	0,000	▲	0,446	↑	0,050	↑
	100 cm	0,007	▲	0,339	↑	0,035	↑
İpsala	5 cm	0,099	▲	0,207	↑	0,029	↑
	10 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,489	↑	0,056	↑
	20 m	<0,0001	▲	0,512	↑	0,069	↑
	50 cm	0,000	▲	0,440	↑	0,050	↑
	100 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,512	↑	0,062	↑
Malkara	5 cm	0,002	▲	0,383	↑	0,050	↑
	10 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,551	↑	0,054	↑
	20 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,536	↑	0,054	↑
	50 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,524	↑	0,044	↑
	100 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,659	↑	0,058	↑
Gökçeada	5 cm	0,335	▲	-0,122	↓	-0,011	↓
	10 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,555	↑	0,063	↑
	20 cm	0,047	▲	0,249	↑	0,022	↑
	50 cm	0,401	▲	0,106	↑	0,010	↑
	100 cm	0,017	▲	0,298	↑	0,050	↑
Çanakkale	5 cm	0,828	▲	-0,029	↓	0,000	↓
	10 cm	0,099	▲	0,208	↑	0,023	↑
	20 cm	0,000	▲	0,493	↑	0,050	↑
	50 cm	0,004	▲	0,362	↑	0,040	↑
	100 cm	<0,0001	▲	0,551	↑	0,052	↑

▲ Significant ▲ Insignificant ↑ Positive (Increase) ↓ Negative (Decrease)

4. DISCUSSION

Annual average air temperatures in the Thracian Peninsula vary between 13.1 °C (Çorlu) and 15.5 °C (Gökçeada). On the contrary, soil temperatures at 5 cm depth vary between 15.4 °C (Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.7 °C (Çanakkale, Gökçeada). At 10 cm depth, soil temperatures were between 15.4 °C (Kırklareli, Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.7 °C (Gökçeada) as at 5 cm. A slight decrease in soil temperatures is observed at 20 cm depth. At this depth, soil temperatures were between 15.3 °C (Lüleburgaz, Çorlu) and 17.5 °C (Gökçeada). Soil temperatures at 50 cm depth are between 15.3 °C (Çorlu) and 17.7 °C (Gökçeada), and soil temperatures at 100 cm depth are between 15.2 °C (Sarıyer) and 17.8 °C (Gökçeada). It is concluded from these values that soil temperature changes at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths between 1990 and 2023 are similar to the change in air temperature, but soil temperatures are constantly above the annual average air temperature values, and the difference between soil temperature and air temperature varies between 1.1 °C and 3.4 °C. It is important to know these soil temperature values and their changes in the research area in terms of sustainable soil management.

In terms of vegetation characteristics, the Istranca Mountains are located in the Öksin-Kolşik or humid forest zone, the Gallipoli Peninsula in the Mediterranean flora zone, and the Ergene Basin in the anthropogenic steppe zone (Dönmez et al., 2012). There are 10 different major soil groups in the Thracian Peninsula: calcareous brown soils, calcareous brown forest soils, brown forest soils, chestnut-colored soils, vertisols, alluvial soils, alluvial coastal soils, rendzinas, hydromorphic soils, and colluvial soils (Altürk et al., 2019). However, the main soil groups found in Tekirdağ province are entisols, inceptisols, vertisols, and alfisols (Özşahin and Eroğlu, 2018b). The annual average soil temperatures in these soil types exhibit a “thermal temperature regime” characteristic in terms of temperature regime. In this soil temperature

regime, the annual average soil temperature at a depth of 50 cm is 15 °C or higher, and the difference in soil temperature between summer and winter is greater than 5 °C (Başyigit and Dinç, 2005; Atalay, 2016).

Monthly average soil temperatures at 5 cm depth in the Thracian Peninsula generally have a significant and positive trend in September, November, December, January, February, and March, while they have a significant and negative trend in April, May, June, and July. At 10 cm, 20 cm, and 50 cm depths, monthly average soil temperatures show a significant and positive trend in the seven months between September and March. The month in which a significant and negative trend is dominant at these depths is June. At 100 cm depth, a significant and positive trend in monthly average soil temperatures is determined in the six months between August and January.

A general evaluation regarding the trend analysis of annual average soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths in the Thracian Peninsula indicates that a statistically significant and positive trend is observed in the annual average soil temperatures of all stations except Kumköy and Sariyer. This is consistent with the significant trend in temperature increases detected in the trend analysis of annual average air temperatures in the Thracian Peninsula (Türkeş, 2012; Eroğlu, 2022).

Atalay (2016) stated that the soil is generally warmer than air in temperate regions in winter, but the subsoil layer is colder than air. In this study, soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm depths were higher than air temperatures in winter.

When the optimum soil temperature range for plant growth is considered to be between 20 °C and 30 °C (Alli & Omofunmi, 2021), it is determined that soil temperatures at 5 cm, 10 cm, and 20 cm depths in the Thracian Peninsula have optimum soil temperatures in the period between May and September, and soil temperatures at 50 cm and 100 cm depths have optimum soil temperatures in the period between June and September. However, it is possible that the significant positive trends detected in soil temperatures may cause changes in the agricultural products grown in the Thracian Peninsula in the following years.

This study is expected to contribute to the studies of many disciplines interested in soil temperatures in the Thracian Peninsula. Consideration of soil temperature characteristics at different depths of the Thracian Peninsula and trends detected in soil temperature time series will be an approach that allows a comprehensive geographical and temporal analysis of crop and plant patterns according to environmental conditions. Moreover, soil temperature trends can be used as a tool to promote the mitigation of various projected environmental problems such as seasonal temperature fluctuations, water scarcity, irrigation demands, and crop rotation.

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